
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE & CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The Indian legal system has not been transformed due to case backlogs, a shortage of judges and staff, extended hearing dates, and lengthy court procedures. All of these concerns contribute to the delay or denial of justice. In recent years, the science of criminal procedure law has been actively discussing the potential applications of artificial intelligence (AI). The notion of “Artificial Intelligence” (AI) is not enshrined in legislation. Still, it is represented by scientific theories, methodologies, and procedures that all have one thing in common: they aim to imitate human cognitive capacities using computers. AI is being used by both criminals and law enforcement, creating a new dynamic in the crime-fighting process. Artificial intelligence can automate regular processes such as case management and document screening. Analysing large amounts of data can reveal trends and predictions, facilitating decision-making. The law enforcement system serves a variety of tasks, including risk assessment, predictive policing, and sentencing. Despite its benefits, technological advancement has created new obstacles for legal regimes as they strive to regulate its usage and protect individual rights. As legal systems attempt to fully understand the implications of emerging technologies for legal decision-making, and with certain restrictions, using artificial intelligence and machine learning in criminal justice raises questions. As these technologies grow, it is critical to recognise their potential benefits and concerns and employ them in a way that respects individual rights and complements human decision-making processes. This paper will look at the use of AI in criminal justice and its possible impact on the future of criminal law in India.

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence is one of the most significant, avant-garde, and transformative methodologies to synchronise, integrate, and augment justice delivery. The term artificial intelligence was first introduced by Arthur McCarthy in 1956. The concept of artificial

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intelligence pertains to the capacity of digital computers or computer-operated robotic systems to execute even the most complex tasks. In the contemporary epoch of Homo sapiens, AI possesses the capability to furnish swifter, more economically feasible, and more effective solutions. Vladimir Putin sagaciously remarked, “*Whoever becomes a leader in this field will rule the world.*” This domain of inquiry encompasses sophisticated and advanced algorithms through which AI assimilates knowledge regarding human behaviour to respond to circumstances and subsequently emulate and react to them based on the inputs received.

AI is frequently classified as a technology; however, it is more accurately characterised as an enabler for various other technologies. The advancements in machine learning paradigms have empowered AI to exceed human intellect in particular functional domains.³ AI can be strategically employed in hybrid warfare and secessionist movements to alter a nation’s developmental trajectory. Recently, India formulated a National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence, designated “AI FOR ALL,” which was promulgated by NITI Aayog in 2018. Furthermore, India actively participates in the Global Partnership on AI (GPAI) Council Chair, enabling collaboration with other nations to facilitate AI governance and intervention. There has been a substantial volume of discourse and enthusiasm regarding the application and integration of AI within the criminal justice system. This study aims to explore the diverse applications of AI in the criminal justice system, with a particular focus on its implications for law enforcement, risk assessment, sentencing, and potential implementation challenges.⁴

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a contemporary focal point of interest. In numerous nations, substantial financial resources are allocated to advance AI research. It is anticipated that AI will instigate profound transformations across various sectors within society, encompassing transportation (for instance, autonomous vehicles), healthcare (such as automated pharmaceutical development), education (including personalised adaptive virtual tutoring systems), and linguistics (for example, instantaneous conversation translations). Additionally, the legal sector is poised to experience significant alterations due to AI developments. On the one hand, advancements in AI may necessitate the introduction of

³ Dr. Sanur Sharma, AI and National Security: Major Power Perspectives & Challenges, IDSA Issue Brief, MPIDSA (February 5, 2023, 03:33 PM) <https://idsa.in/issuebrief/ai-and-national-security-ssharma-120922>

⁴ Rishav Anand, Artificial Intelligence and its Role in the Criminal Justice System: A Comprehensive Legal Analysis, The Amikus Qraie (February 22, 2023, 03:35 PM) https://theamikusqraie.com/artificial-intelligence-and-its-role-in-the-criminal-justice-system-a-comprehensive-legal-analysis/#_ftn1

novel, alternative, or additional regulatory frameworks; on the other hand, AI is likely to provide an increasing array of applications beneficial for legal research and practice.⁵

In contemporary society, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has permeated nearly every facet of our existence, significantly shaping our decision-making processes. The ramifications of AI on societal structures are profound, as individuals, institutions, and governmental entities employ it through diverse applications. Although AI lacks a statutory definition, it is articulated within the scientific domain through various methodologies and frameworks, typically characterised as the application of machines to replicate human cognitive functions. The proliferation of AI technologies has accelerated at an unprecedented pace, with advancements being harnessed for the collective benefit of humanity across numerous domains.

Historically, 'criminal law' and 'technology' domains have been perceived as disparate entities. The discipline of criminal procedure law is engaged in ongoing discourse regarding the prospective integration of artificial intelligence within judicial settings. The shift towards a digital paradigm engenders profound transformations, not solely concerning criminal activities but also in the methodologies employed during investigative processes. The duty of administering justice rests upon humanity, and this abrupt digital evolution in societal interactions is influencing the efficacy of this endeavour. The criminal justice system (CJS) must optimise the advantages of technology and AI to the fullest extent. It is imperative for experts from diverse sectors, including policymakers, technologists, and legal professionals, to collaborate for the overarching benefit of society, particularly about the criminal justice framework.⁶

Due to the protracted nature of case resolutions, a deficiency in the number of judicial officers and judges, and prolonged durations of court proceedings culminating in extensive legal processes, the judicial system in India has yet to undergo reform. These challenges contribute to delays in judicial proceedings, which equates to a denial of justice. Integrating Artificial Intelligence within a judicial administration framework necessitates implementation to enhance the efficacy of legal and law enforcement mechanisms. Sharad Arvind Bobde, the

⁵ Custers, Bart, AI in Criminal Law: An Overview of AI Applications in Substantive and Procedural Criminal Law (January 20, 2022). Custers, B.H.M. (2022) AI in Criminal Law: An Overview of AI Applications in Substantive and Procedural Criminal Law, in: B.H.M. Custers & E. Fosch Villaronga (eds.) Law and Artificial Intelligence, Heidelberg: Springer, p. 205-223., Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4331759> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4331759>

⁶ Anoushka Bidwalkar, Use of Artificial Intelligence in Criminal Justice System, National Law Institute University Bhopal Cell for Law & Technology (March 9, 2023, 10:54 AM) <https://clt.nliu.ac.in/?p=431>

former Chief Justice of India, articulated, *“There exists a potential for the development of Artificial Intelligence within the court system. This is solely to ensure that the unwarranted delays in the administration of justice are mitigated...We must utilise every talent and skill to guarantee justice within a reasonable timeframe. A delay in justice cannot justify any individual to take the law into their own hands. However, we as courts must guarantee that there is no unwarranted delay in delivering justice.”*⁷

Enumerating the volume of cases pending adjudication in each court, he underscored the necessity for developing artificial intelligence tailored to the judiciary. The confluence of artificial intelligence with the concept of electronic courts is thus likely to facilitate the amalgamation of information and technology within the judicial system.⁸

Many methodologies utilising artificial intelligence as an instrument for public safety are currently under examination. In both governmental and commercial domains, facial recognition represents a prominent application of AI technology that is extensively implemented. For example, intelligence operatives routinely employ facial images to ascertain an individual's identity and location. The exhaustive analysis of the vast array of potentially pertinent photos and videos necessitates considerable time and effort, and there is the potential for human error to arise due to fatigue and other factors. Unlike humans, machines possess an inherent capacity for unwavering endurance. In pursuit of ensuring secure and efficient commuter traffic across diverse locations and varying weather, lighting, and traffic conditions, the United States Department of Transportation is actively engaged in the research, development, and testing of automated traffic accident detection systems based on video analysis, aiming to enhance public safety. Applying artificial intelligence algorithms to evaluate radiological images in the medical domain may yield significant implications for criminal justice and medical forensics, particularly in elucidating the cause and manner of death.

Furthermore, artificial intelligence algorithms have been investigated across multiple disciplines within forensic science, including deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) analysis. Additionally, artificial intelligence is swiftly establishing itself as a pivotal technology for fraud detection. Online enterprises such as PayPal mitigate fraudulent activities by

⁷ Snigdha Choudhury, ‘Possibility of Developing Artificial Intelligence for Court System, says CJI Bobde’ India Today(Bengaluru, January 12 2020, 09:14 IST) <https://www.indiatoday.in/india/story/artificial-intelligence-court-system-cji-bobde-1636116-2020-01-12>

⁸ Apoorva Chandra, Artificial Intelligence & the Criminal Justice System of India, Vol.2 Issue 3, JLRJS, 1161, 1162-1163 (2023) <https://jlrjs.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/142.-Apoorva-Chandra.pdf>

consistently training their fraud detection algorithms with substantial datasets to recognise and anticipate anomalous patterns while adapting to emerging trends.⁹

Numerous scholarly investigations have been undertaken regarding applying artificial intelligence within criminal procedures globally. A subset of these investigations indicates that AI presents substantial opportunities to enhance the legal system's transparency, predictability, and standardisation. Conversely, additional research highlights that AI engenders various concerns attributable to the limitations inherent in existing software capabilities within the information technology sector. In light of these dual considerations, it is imperative for governmental authorities and legal practitioners engaged in judicial and criminal processes to recognise the prospective advantages of AI while closely monitoring its efficacy and progression in real-time contexts. In adjudicating criminal cases, the accused's intent constitutes a paramount consideration. Many factors, which may elude the analytical capabilities of AI, can influence an individual's behaviour.

In conducting investigations, numerous variables come into play, including the individual's familial background, educational attainment, perceptions of guilt, and other pertinent characteristics. Preserving an individual's honour and dignity and safeguarding personal data must not be disregarded within the criminal justice framework. Consequently, it is posited that artificial intelligence may lack the capacity to address all the issues that emerge during criminal proceedings adequately. Nonetheless, artificial intelligence has the potential to be effectively employed in the analysis of statistical data, the facilitation of legal document preparation, the exploration of online resources for pertinent information, and the rendering of decisions on the classification of criminal acts. Stakeholders should rigorously scrutinise the scientific legitimacy of implementing artificial intelligence algorithms, the operational relevance attributed to their various dimensions, and the conclusions' soundness. Therefore, the judicial authorities should decide on AI utilisation within the criminal justice system.

Owing to the predictive capabilities of AI, it has witnessed a marked increase in adoption within the domains of criminology, law, and forensics. At present, algorithmic risk assessments are extensively utilised within law enforcement agencies. Predictive policing methodologies and assessments are employed to ascertain the likelihood of an individual's court appearance or potential criminal activity. Moreover, the digital revolution that has

⁹ Shiwani & Dr.Namah Datta, Research Paper on Artificial Intelligence & Criminal Justice System, Vol.11 Issue 1, IJCRT, 223, 224 (2023) <https://ijert.org/papers/IJCRT2301151.pdf>

permeated the globe over the past decade yields profound implications for every aspect of criminal justice administration. The shift towards a digital paradigm instils significant transformations like criminality and investigation methodologies. The obligation to deliver justice is incumbent upon us and has been influenced by this abrupt digital transition. This migration to a digital environment has afforded us expedited access to data and innovative investigative frameworks predicated on the mining and analysis of extensive data sets. As a consequence of the 2019 pandemic, courts have undergone a comprehensive digital transformation, facilitating unrestricted access to any requisite legal information.¹⁰

Criminal justice systems worldwide employ various resources, including information technology, to reduce felonies and crimes. With Schumpeter's predicted technological advance and creative destruction, it would seem strange for the criminal justice industry not to consider AI's potential contribution and utility. However, AI is only a tool, and because a tool is only as good as its user, it is critical to assess potential negative externalities of AI applications in criminal justice to avoid counterproductive outcomes such as bias and inaccuracies. Many AI applications are still in their early stages. Criminal justice, particularly law enforcement, must then consider the use of AI in terms of fundamental human rights principles such as privacy and non-discrimination. In light of the growing belief that AI algorithms are more objective and intelligent than humans, although they can convey human error.

Although the operational mechanisms of artificial intelligence are devoid of any human involvement, they are nonetheless conceived and developed by humans, thus indicating a potential for error. The datasets employed in AI algorithms to derive outcomes are inherently comprised of human-generated data, which signifies the preexistence of human biases that are subsequently perpetuated in the results yielded by AI. Empirical research studies have demonstrated that deploying AI may result in certain demographic groups being subjected to a disproportionate frequency of stops and searches by law enforcement agencies, undermining the principles of fairness, equality, and equity for citizens. For instance, the application of AI in surveilling criminal 'hotspots' can exacerbate geographical discrimination, as these areas are subjected to heightened police scrutiny compared to others, culminating in elevated arrests within such AI-monitored locales.

¹⁰ Christopher Rigano, Using Artificial Intelligence to Address Criminal Justice Needs, National Institute of Justice (March 17, 2023, 03:48 PM) <https://nij.ojp.gov/topics/articles/using-artificial-intelligence-address-criminal-justice-needs>

It is crucial to emphasise that the databases utilised by law enforcement are predominantly operated by private corporations, such as Clearview, recognised as the largest facial recognition network globally established for law enforcement purposes. Although Clearview is contractually obligated to governmental entities, this arrangement suggests a partial delegation of specific sovereign functions to private enterprises, which may precipitate adverse ramifications, including the creation of compromised databases or cyber intrusions, thereby violating the privacy rights of numerous citizens. To mitigate discrimination and the infringement of fundamental rights, the integration of AI within law enforcement necessitates a robust framework of accountability, fairness, and transparency.¹¹

II. AI'S INVOLVEMENT IN CRIMINAL ACTIVITIES

As artificial intelligence technology progresses rapidly within the Indian context, its participation in illicit activities has become a significant concern in jurisprudence. The convergence of artificial intelligence and criminality has resulted in a novel category of offenders who exploit AI algorithms to execute intricate cybercrimes, hacking endeavours, and various other unlawful activities. One of the most formidable challenges confronting the judicial system is identifying and attributing crimes perpetrated by AI. Offenders utilise anonymisation technologies and AI-enhanced evasion methodologies, rendering it increasingly difficult for law enforcement agencies to trace the origins of the assaults or ascertain the identities of the guilty parties. The legal uncertainties surrounding the role of AI in criminal endeavours further exacerbate the situation, as the issues of liability and accountability become progressively convoluted when addressing autonomous and ostensibly self-governing AI algorithms. In the medical domain, artificial intelligence assists healthcare professionals in diagnosing ailments with greater precision and practicality. AI algorithms can scrutinise medical imaging, such as X-rays, CT scans, and MRIs, to unveil anomalies and facilitate the early detection of diseases.

Additionally, artificial intelligence contributes to formulating personalised treatment strategies for patients by examining their genetic profiles and medical histories. This approach may culminate in more efficacious treatments and reduced adverse side effects. The COVID-19 pandemic expedited the integration of telemedicine in India, with AI playing a pivotal role in enhancing the effectiveness of remote consultations. AI-driven diagnostic

¹¹ Asma Idder & Stephane Coulaux, Artificial Intelligence in Criminal Justice: Invasion or Revolution? International Bar Association (April 7, 2023, 03:55 PM) <https://www.ibanet.org/dec-21-ai-criminal-justice>

instruments and telemonitoring systems have been employed to extend medical care to patients from a distance. Furthermore, artificial intelligence bolsters medical research by analysing extensive datasets and discerning patterns and trends that could catalyse advancements in the comprehension and treatment of diseases. AI is essential in drug discovery and development, as it can scrutinise vast datasets to identify potential pharmacological candidates and forecast their efficacy, potentially hastening the drug development timeline. In scenarios where physicians or developers may not possess the intent to inflict harm, the possibility exists that if AI executes an erroneous decision due to negligence, it could inadvertently result in a criminal offence. This situation arises from the fact that negligence is regarded as one of the fundamental elements of mens rea.¹²

The progressive utilisation of artificial intelligence (AI) in illicit activities presents extensive ramifications for data privacy and security within the Indian context. Perpetrators are exploiting AI algorithms to collect and misappropriate personal information, thereby undermining the privacy and safety of individuals. Given the continuously escalating dependence on AI across diverse sectors, the risk of data breaches and unauthorised access to confidential information constitutes a paramount concern for the legal profession. As AI-facilitated crimes increase in intricacy and magnitude, legal frameworks must evolve to protect citizens' data and ensure that data privacy statutes remain current and enforceable. Another significant dimension of AI's engagement in criminal enterprises is its capacity to exacerbate social disparities and biases embedded in the justice system. AI algorithms employed in predictive policing and law enforcement may inadvertently perpetuate pre-existing biases, disproportionately targeting specific communities or individuals. This phenomenon can lead to civil and human rights violations, necessitating meticulous scrutiny and regulation of AI applications within the legal sphere. The Indian legal system is compelled to proactively confront these challenges to uphold the principles of equity and justice while integrating AI technologies into its operations. The proliferation of AI-generated deceptive content, such as deepfakes, introduces novel challenges for India's legal framework. Deepfakes can manipulate evidence, damage reputations, and disseminate misinformation, undermining judicial proceedings' integrity. Establishing the authenticity of evidence and confirming the accuracy of information emerge as critical concerns for judicial bodies and

¹² Hifajatali Sayyed, Artificial Intelligence & Criminal Liability in India: Exploring Legal Implications & Challenges, Vol.1o No.1, CSSLCCJ, 1, 3-4 (2024) https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379955663_Artificial_intelligence_and_criminal_liability_in_India_exploring_legal_implications_and_challenges

legal practitioners. Legal professionals must remain vigilant in identifying and contesting the authenticity of AI-generated material to maintain the integrity of the legal process. The emergence of automated financial crimes represents yet another domain where AI's involvement engenders substantial legal complications. Offenders can exploit AI algorithms to detect vulnerabilities and flaws within economic systems, thereby facilitating money laundering, fraud, and other illicit financial activities. Identifying and prosecuting such offences may necessitate specialised legal insight and a comprehensive understanding of criminals' complex AI-driven strategies. Enhancing India's financial regulatory frameworks and fostering collaboration with international counterparts to address cross-border financial crimes are essential to alleviating this threat. The legal community must also contemplate the broader ethical considerations surrounding AI's role in criminal activities. The conscientious and moral advancement of AI algorithms is crucial to ensuring that these technologies are not employed to undermine societal norms and legal standards.¹³

As artificial intelligence technology advances, the notion of autonomous weaponry concurrently evolves. While such technologies are not yet widespread in India, the potential for the misuse of AI in creating autonomous armaments raises significant legal and ethical dilemmas. These weapons may function independently of human oversight, resulting in unforeseen repercussions and indiscriminate assaults. The legal fraternity must remain alert in observing international trends related to AI-enhanced weaponry and advocate for stringent regulations to avert their exploitation. Tackling AI's role in unlawful activities necessitates a cooperative endeavour among legislators, legal professionals, AI technologists, and civil society stakeholders. The Indian legal framework must remain at the vanguard of technological progress and exhibit agility in adjusting to the changing landscape of AI-facilitated offences. Continuous evaluation and modification of policies are imperative to align with the swiftly evolving technological milieu and guarantee that India's legal infrastructure remains efficient in countering AI-associated criminal endeavours. To promote innovation and progress while protecting against the misuse of AI, India must achieve a nuanced equilibrium between encouraging technological advancement and enforcing rigorous legal measures. This equilibrium will enable the legal system to effectively address emerging threats posed by AI-driven criminality without obstructing technological progress or violating individual liberties.

¹³ Ibid at 4

Furthermore, fostering international cooperation and exchanging information will be essential in tackling the transnational characteristics of cybercrime and AI-related illicit activities. The involvement of AI in criminal undertakings within India presents many legal obstacles that necessitate a proactive and comprehensive strategy from the legal community. As AI technology progresses, it is critical to continuously assess and modify legal frameworks to address the ever-shifting terrain of AI-driven offences. Achieving a balance between innovation and regulation is vital for leveraging the advantages of AI while minimising its potential for misuse in criminal contexts. By proactively confronting these challenges through collaborative efforts, India can establish a robust legal framework that protects against AI-related criminal activities while simultaneously promoting technological advancement for the collective benefit of society.¹⁴

III. AI IN CRIME PREVENTION, INVESTIGATION & PROSECUTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly recognised as a formidable tool in crime prevention within an era marked by swift technological advancements. As societies strive to enhance safety and security, AI presents innovative methodologies to augment traditional law enforcement practices and address evolving challenges. By harnessing the capabilities of AI, we can transform crime prevention strategies, empower communities, and foster a more secure society. Conventional crime prevention methodologies often emphasise reactive measures, whereby law enforcement intervenes post-incident. In contrast, AI facilitates a fundamental shift towards proactive and preventive strategies. By scrutinising extensive datasets, AI systems can identify patterns, detect anomalies, and yield critical insights regarding potential criminal behaviour. This proactive methodology allows law enforcement to intervene before the occurrence of crimes, thereby mitigating risks and safeguarding communities. One of the paramount attributes of AI in crime prevention is its ability to process and analyse substantial datasets from diverse sources. AI algorithms can deliver real-time insights by integrating data from surveillance systems, social media, public records, and other pertinent sources. This capability enables law enforcement to more effectively pinpoint crime hotspots, predict criminal trends, and allocate resources efficiently. For instance, AI-enhanced predictive policing frameworks can aid law enforcement agencies in identifying

¹⁴ Ibid

areas with heightened crime likelihood, thereby facilitating proactive officer deployment, preventing incidents, and fostering community trust.¹⁵

Moreover, AI possesses the potential to enhance the capabilities and efficiency of existing surveillance frameworks substantially. AI-augmented video analytics can autonomously monitor and analyse video feeds, flagging suspicious activities and alleviating the workload on human operators. Facial recognition technologies can assist in identifying individuals implicated in criminal activities, support investigative efforts, and expedite the apprehension of suspects. By integrating AI into surveillance systems, law enforcement can extend coverage over larger areas, diminish response times, and enhance the efficacy of crime prevention initiatives. Engagement and collaboration within the community are essential elements of successful crime prevention. In this context, AI can serve as a catalyst, fortifying the connections between law enforcement agencies and the communities they serve. AI-driven chatbots and virtual assistants can provide community members with accessible and tailored information, addressing their concerns and disseminating crime prevention recommendations. Furthermore, AI algorithms can analyse community-generated data, such as reports of suspicious activities, to assist in identifying emerging trends and facilitating targeted responses. Through AI-enabled platforms, community members can actively engage in crime prevention initiatives, contributing to the creation of safer neighbourhoods and promoting a shared sense of responsibility.¹⁶

However, as we integrate artificial intelligence into crime prevention strategies, ethical considerations and privacy safeguards must be prioritised. Achieving a harmonious equilibrium between public safety and preserving individual freedoms is essential. Comprehensive policies and legal frameworks must be established to ensure the responsible deployment of AI systems, safeguarding privacy, and mitigating biases and data misuse. The transparency of AI algorithms and the processes involved in decision-making are vital for fostering public trust and preventing potential misuse. By harnessing the analytical capabilities of AI, predictive insights, and community engagement tools, we can proactively address criminal activities, empower local communities, and cultivate a safer societal environment. In exploring artificial intelligence opportunities, it is crucial to emphasise

¹⁵ Dr. Debdatta Das & Dr. Paramita Bhattacharya, Artificial Intelligence & Criminal Justice System in India, Vol.8 Issue 4, NUJSJRS, 2, 4-5 (2023) <https://www.nujs.edu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/vol-8-iss-4-1.pdf>

¹⁶ Puneet Gawali & Reeta Sony, The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Improving Criminal Justice System: Indian Perspective, ResearchGate (April 7, 2023) https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350346087_The_Role_of_Artificial_Intelligence_in_Improving_Criminal_Justice_System_Indian_Perspective

ethical considerations, uphold transparency, and foster collaboration among technology experts, law enforcement entities, and the communities they serve. The application of AI in crime prevention can create a world where individuals can thrive in secure and harmonious surroundings, provided it is executed responsibly and inclusively. The prevention of crime constitutes the foremost line of defence against criminal activity. Artificial intelligence can assist law enforcement agencies in forecasting and averting criminal occurrences by discerning patterns in criminal behaviour.

Furthermore, AI algorithms can aid police forces in pinpointing high-risk zones and individuals based on crime trends and various data sources. Additionally, AI can be pivotal in recognising potential threats and vulnerabilities within critical infrastructure, transport systems, and public venues. For instance, AI can scrutinise CCTV footage to detect suspicious behaviours, locate missing persons, and oversee crowds during events.

The criminal justice system has severe obstacles, including a shortage of resources to investigate and solve crimes. AI may help speed up the investigative process by analysing enormous volumes of data and detecting patterns and connections that people find difficult to detect independently. This can assist law enforcement organisations in identifying suspects and collecting evidence more efficiently and accurately. AI can also help with forensic analysis, which is critical in solving many crimes. For example, AI may analyse DNA samples, fingerprints, and other evidence to identify suspects or connect crimes to past instances.

The integration of Artificial Intelligence in prosecutorial functions can enhance the efficiency of the legal framework, mitigate procedural delays, and ensure the prompt and effective administration of justice. AI facilitates the systematic examination of evidence and identifying critical data that contribute to constructing a robust case. Furthermore, AI aids in recognising trends and patterns in criminal conduct, thereby assisting prosecutors in making judicious determinations regarding plea negotiations and judicial outcomes. AI empowers prosecutors to formulate compelling cases and tests by evaluating historical case data, including judicial outcomes and favourable results. In April 2021, the Supreme Court of India inaugurated its inaugural Artificial Intelligence platform, SUPACE (Supreme Court Portal for Assistance in Courts Efficiency). At the launch, the then Hon'ble Chief Justice of India, S. A. Bobde, articulated that the Supreme Court is incorporating Artificial Intelligence into its standard operational procedures. He alluded to the noteworthy defeat of grandmaster Garry

Kasparov by the computer Deep Blue in 1997, which exemplified how previously obscure AI had become increasingly accessible to the layperson. During the introduction of SUPACE, Hon'ble CJI S. A. Bobde delineated that this AI portal would be designated for data collection and analysis rather than for formulating judicial decisions. As reported in May 2021, statistics from the National Judicial Data Grid indicated that approximately 3.81 crore cases were pending in various district and taluka courts across India, with over one lakh cases remaining unresolved for over three decades. AI has demonstrated significant advantages across diverse sectors, including healthcare, agriculture, climate change mitigation, disaster prediction, and governance. Nonetheless, the deployment of AI has also engendered concerns regarding its capacity for mass surveillance, which may infringe upon privacy rights and protections, as well as its potential role in the propagation of disinformation.¹⁷

IV. APPLICATION OF AI IN THE LEGAL INDUSTRY

The primary areas where artificial intelligence is employed or may find use soon are mentioned below.¹⁸

A. Use of AI by law enforcement agencies

Artificial Intelligence (AI) can enhance law enforcement agencies' operational efficacy through various methodologies. This encompasses incorporating biometric data, including facial recognition, voice identification, blood group classification, and fingerprint analysis of diverse suspects, thereby facilitating the investigative process and the surveillance of criminal activities. AI-driven technological frameworks can be proficiently employed to assist investigative personnel in adhering to procedural protocols during investigations. This implementation mitigates the likelihood of procedural inaccuracies by law enforcement officials. Moreover, it is feasible to establish an AI-augmented digital repository that encompasses information regarding offences, operational patterns, and analogous crimes perpetrated across different locales. The utilisation of AI has already established a considerable presence in this domain, as evidenced by instances such as the AI-facilitated facial recognition system designated as ABHED (AI-Based Human Efface Detection), which Staqu Technologies developed in collaboration with Punjab and Rajasthan Police; AI-enhanced apparatus introduced by the Odisha Police for the analytical evaluation of crime

¹⁷ Dr. Debdatta Das & Dr. Paramita Bhattacharya, *Supra* Note 15 at 6-7

¹⁸ Gagandeep Singh Narula, *AI and Indian Criminal Justice System*, iPleaders (January 13, 2024, 09:14 PM) <https://blog.ipleaders.in/ai-and-indian-criminal-justice-system/>

data; TRINETRA, an AI-driven facial recognition application implemented by the Uttar Pradesh Police; the E-Pragati database inaugurated by the Government of Andhra Pradesh; and the establishment of an AI centre by the Delhi Police to address criminal activities, in partnership with IIT Delhi. AI can also assist jail officials in monitoring illicit activity within or near the facility. Illegal actions within jails may be simply and efficiently monitored using AI-based surveillance systems and drone technology. For example, in collaboration with Staqu Technologies, the Uttar Pradesh government has built JARVIS, an AI-based video analytics platform that scans information from CCTV footage throughout jails.

B. Use of AI by the judicial system

In the Indian legal system, the principle of stare decisis significantly influences the adjudication of cases. This principle mandates the observance of rulings from superior courts as a benchmark for judicial determinations. Implementing an artificial intelligence-driven database containing judicial decisions would facilitate this laborious process. AI technologies can accurately transcribe statements presented during court proceedings, thereby minimising the potential for human error. This innovation promotes transparency in the execution of trials. The traditional manual processes of issuing summons, managing witness attendance, and scheduling subsequent hearings often result in unnecessary delays. An AI-integrated system can effectively mitigate these delays and streamline the trial procedures. The application of artificial intelligence can condense or clarify the content of legal documents, thus enabling judges to expedite the issuance of interim orders. In criminal cases, judges must make various determinations, such as granting bail to defendants. Using AI-enhanced technologies simplifies these decision-making processes, assisting judges in assessing case outcomes. For instance, the Public Safety Assessment (PSA) developed by the Arnold Foundation represents a prominent AI tool utilised within the judicial system in the United States.

The Supreme Court has introduced an AI-based translation tool known as SUVAS (Supreme Court Vidhik Anuvaad Software) to facilitate the translation of English judicial documents into nine regional languages. This initiative aims to enhance the general populace's comprehension of legal documents and court proceedings. In collaboration with the National Informatics Centre, the Supreme Court has also implemented an official multilingual mobile application designed to provide real-time updates on court proceedings, circulars, reports, and other legal information accessible to litigants, attorneys, and the general public. The

application is available on iOS in English, Hindi, and six additional regional languages. Furthermore, the Supreme Court developed the SUPACE (Supreme Court Portal for Assistance in Courts Efficiency) portal to analyse extensive datasets related to case filings, thereby assisting judges in identifying salient facts and issues in new cases.

C. Use of AI by law firms and legal professionals

AI assists advocates in preparing discovery answers responding pleadings, and other documents simply by uploading a complaint or discovery request with jurisdictional criteria. LegalMation is AI-powered software that helps advocates and experts speed up litigation. AI-trained machine learning algorithms classify and cluster various documents by identifying hidden commonalities. AI may also aid with contract analysis and document evaluation. Cyril Amarchand Mangaldas, a well-known business, collaborated with Kira Systems to offer AI-based machine learning software to discover and analyse problematic provisions/clauses in agreements by exploring large volumes of web resources.

V. POTENTIAL BENEFITS OF AI IN THE LEGAL PROFESSION

a. Law Firms & Lawyers

The advancement of AI technology enables attorneys to increase their productivity, cut expenses, and focus on more critical tasks. AI may do mechanical and regular operations such as document and contract evaluation, legal research, and data analysis. This can result in higher productivity and profitability for legal firms. However, AI is currently incapable of handling more sophisticated activities such as deal structuring, negotiation, advocacy, and legal representation. As a result, adopting AI may lead to fewer billable hours for legal firms. While bigger organisations may have the resources to incorporate AI systems, smaller enterprises may struggle to stay up with technological costs while being cost-effective.¹⁹

b. Indian Judiciary

Since 2021, the Supreme Court has used an AI-controlled tool to digest information and provide it to justices for decision-making. It is not involved in the decision-making process. Another technology utilised by the Supreme Court of India is SUVAS, which translates legal

¹⁹ Aditi Prabhu, Artificial intelligence in the context of the Indian legal profession and judicial system, Bar & Bench (August 12, 2023, 01:01 PM) <https://www.barandbench.com/columns/artificial-intelligence-in-context-of-legal-profession-and-indian-judicial-system>

documents from English to vernacular languages and vice versa. In *Jaswinder Singh v. State of Punjab*, the Punjab & Haryana High Court denied a bail plea based on the prosecution's accusations that the petitioner was involved in a vicious, deadly attack. The sitting court sought information from ChatGPT to acquire a broader perspective on granting bail when cruelty is involved. However, it is crucial to emphasise that this reference to ChatGPT does not represent a view on the case's merits, and the trial court will not consider these remarks. The reference was designed to offer a more comprehensive knowledge of bail jurisprudence where cruelty is involved.

c. Application of AI in India's Criminal Justice System

AI's incorporation within the Indian criminal justice framework has been progressively advancing, particularly in domains such as predictive policing, case management, and forensic analysis. It is pertinent to acknowledge that the operational environment may have undergone transformations since then, and particular advancements or modifications might have occurred.²⁰

1. **Predictive Policing:** In the Indian context, some law enforcement agencies have initiated the exploration of AI applications for predictive policing. AI algorithms systematically evaluate historical crime data to discern patterns and identify potential crime-prone areas. This intelligence aids law enforcement in optimising resource allocation to mitigate criminal occurrences. However, this application engenders apprehensions regarding algorithmic biases and underscores the necessity for transparency in the decision-making processes employed by these algorithms.
2. **Case Management and Legal Research:** AI-driven tools are increasingly utilised for case management and legal research. These technological instruments facilitate legal practitioners in the analysis of extensive legal datasets, the identification of pertinent precedents, and the streamlining of administrative functions. Such advancements can improve the efficiency of legal proceedings and support the accurate application of legal principles.
3. **Facial Recognition and Surveillance:** Certain law enforcement bodies have investigated using facial recognition technology to identify and monitor individuals. While this technological advancement can prove instrumental in crime resolution, it

²⁰ Muskan Shokeen & Vinit Sharma, Artificial intelligence and criminal justice system in India: A critical study, Volume 5 Issue 4, IJLPSR, 156, 161-162 (2023) <https://www.lawjournals.net/assets/archives/2023/vol5issue4/5123.pdf>

simultaneously raises significant concerns regarding privacy and civil liberties. Achieving an equitable compromise between public safety imperatives and individual rights presents an ongoing challenge.

4. **Forensic Analysis:** The application of AI in forensic analysis encompasses the assessment of digital evidence, fingerprints, and DNA. Automated systems can assist forensic specialists in efficiently processing and analysing extensive datasets, potentially expediting criminal investigations.
5. **Efficiency in Case Backlog Management:** The Indian judicial framework frequently encounters difficulties with case backlogs. AI applications can alleviate these challenges by automating routine operations, aiding in document processing, and promoting a more seamless workflow management system.
6. **Sentencing and Risk Assessment:** AI algorithms are under consideration to assist judicial authorities in determining appropriate sentencing by evaluating various parameters, including the gravity of the offence and the offender's criminal record. Risk assessment tools, supported by AI, strive to deliver insights into recidivism probability and inform decisions related to parole or probation.
7. **Challenges and Ethical Considerations:** The assimilation of AI into India's criminal justice system is fraught with challenges. Issues such as algorithmic bias, data privacy concerns, and the necessity for transparent and explicable AI frameworks are of paramount importance. Ensuring that AI technologies are consistent with constitutional tenets and human rights standards is imperative.
8. **Public Awareness and Accountability:** As AI technologies gain traction within the criminal justice, an escalating demand exists for heightened public awareness and accountability. Transparency regarding AI utilisation, public education concerning its capabilities and limitations, and establishing accountability mechanisms in instances of misuse are critical considerations.

It is imperative to acknowledge that the application of artificial intelligence within the Indian criminal justice framework is characterised by its rapid evolution, with the possibility that new policies or regulatory measures may have been instituted since my most recent update. Maintaining an awareness of the most current legal advancements and ethical considerations on incorporating AI into the criminal justice system in India is vital for a thorough comprehension of the subject matter.

VI. Conclusion & Suggestion

The argument over whether AI is a benefit or a scourge continues. The primary goal of using AI in the legal industry and everyday life is to simplify processes. AI will soon replace tiresome employment and the personnel required to perform these repetitive operations. AI will help lawyers and law firms become more precise and focused in the legal system. AI can reduce time and boost efficiency, leading to a speedier justice delivery. It can increase productivity and production, allowing attorneys and legal firms to complete more work in less time. It may also automate repetitive operations like drafting standard-form contracts and proofreading. However, the application of AI in the legal profession is limited since computers need more originality, inventiveness, and new talents. AI cannot offer reasoned judgements on previously discovered legal topics because it lacks the logic and reason of the human brain. The use of technology always carries the danger of a data breach. Legal information is highly delicate, and client-attorney confidentiality cannot be jeopardised for expediency. Finally, the growing usage of AI is expected to create unemployment in the legal business.

Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to drastically change India's criminal justice system by increasing efficiency, transparency, and equity. Its applications include predictive policing, case management, legal research, and evidence analysis, which can help to speed operations and minimise backlog. However, AI must be used cautiously to avoid prejudice, privacy, and ethical difficulties. Ensuring that AI systems are open, responsible, and subject to human monitoring is critical to preventing perpetuating injustices and violating rights. As India modernises its legal infrastructure, rigorous regulation and coordination among engineers, politicians, and legal experts will be critical to capitalising on AI's benefits while ensuring justice and fairness.